

**PRESERVING MOTHER NATURE TO ENLARGE THE PLANT WORLD
TODAY IS ONE OF THE MAIN ISSUES OF THE DAY.**

Roziyeva Nazira Yodgorovna

ruzievanazira911@gmail.com

Teacher of Termiz State University of Engineering and Agrotechnology

Chorshambiyeva Shohida Ikram's daughter.

Eshboyeva Zarina Rustam's daughter

Students of Termiz State University of Engineering and Agrotechnology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14053734>

ABSTRACT In this article, the issue that is considered urgent today, i.e., increasing the number of plants in the preservation of mother nature is of great importance today, the need to increase the number of plants in preserving the purity of the atmosphere, as a result of which a healthy environment will be created in the future. it is said to give concepts about the basic source for creating a style.

KEY WORDS: mother nature, conservation, natural resources, ecological education, ecological education, ecological outlook, atmospheric air, public health, nature protection.

INTRODUCTION: protection of mother nature, rational use of its resources is an important task. The climate changes that are happening on earth are proof of how serious the situation is. Therefore, on this day, we should all unite and contribute to the protection of the environment and the preservation of our motherland. Knowledge of the laws of interdependence and development of processes occurring in nature is of great importance for the rational use of natural resources. It is impossible to assess the natural processes, to take them into account, to predict the future consequences of any impact on nature, components of nature. The interaction of man with nature accelerates as the development of society and production methods become more and more perfect, from nature, its wealth, construction and production techniques, means of communication change large cities, create large oases, cultural landscapes, grow fruitful crops and fruits, productive livestock. gives But sometimes overestimating human power without deep study and influencing nature can lead to unusable nature, its destruction and pollution. Such a scene is observed throughout the history of mankind. due to the fact that the scale of human use of nature is not very large, in connection with June 5 - the World Environment Day, certain works are being carried out to eliminate environmental problems, preserve the purity and naturalness of mother nature, and deliver it to the next generation in its entirety. In particular, a number of important strategic

documents aimed at ensuring environmental safety, improving the ecological situation and adapting to climate change, preserving biodiversity, and waste management have been adopted in our country.

In order to preserve Mother Nature, protect it and use natural resources wisely The national project "Green Space" put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is highly appreciated by the international community for its large-scale reforms aimed at improving the ecological situation. One of the main ideas of the Ecological Party of Uzbekistan is to further expand the existing green spaces in our country. within the framework of the nationwide project, an initiative to plant 1 billion tree saplings was determined. various fruit and ornamental plants are being planted. Also, "Green Gardens" and "Green Public Parks" are being established. In particular, 444 "Green Parks" and 160 public parks have been established in 2024 alone. In order to adapt to climate change, mitigate the consequences of the Aral disaster and further develop the area along the Aral, improve the social and economic conditions in the region, and restore biological diversity, 1 million people have been planted in the dry bottom of the Aral Sea so far. Saxovol and desert plants were planted on 800,000 hectares of land. During the current year, 100,000 hectares of Saxovol and desert plants were planted in the dry bottom of Arol, and 100,000 hectares of Saxovol and desert plants in Bukhara, Khorezm and Navoi regions in the region of the Arol region. Planting of plants has been decided, and today the work is being carried out rapidly. incomparable Today, our party is steadily achieving concrete results in reforming and stabilizing society's life, finding solutions to environmental problems, promoting green economy and green development, and implementing major goals that serve the people's well-being.

ONCLUSION: In general, it is an important task to preserve mother nature and use its resources wisely. The climate changes that are happening on earth are proof of how serious the situation is. Therefore, on this day, we should all unite and contribute to the protection of the environment and the preservation of our motherland.

References:

1. Shamshetova A. "Psychological-pedagogical aspects of environmental education" Public education. - Tashkent. -2009. - No. 2. -B. 113,117
2. Kholiyev I, Ikromov A. Ecology (for vocational colleges) study guide Tashkent - Labor publishing house - 2001y-207 b
3. Ergashev A. General ecology. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2003. - 464 p.
4. Ismailova Sh. "Interactive methods in the formation of ecological culture" Public education. - Tashkent, - 2008. -2 - no. - B. 38-42.

THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

5. N.Y. Roziyeva. The model of formation of environmental education for students by preserving and respecting nature Namangan State Scientific University newsletter 2024. y 1 issue.

